

Zitterbewegung and Different Spin States?

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In a number of notes [2]-[9], it was shown that Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2=p^2 + m^2$ (1) could be written as a linear 2x2 matrix equation, very much like the Dirac equation. It was found that $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\sqrt{c+v}, \sqrt{c-v})$ was a positive energy eigenstate so that $.5(1+v)$ and $.5(1-v)$ ($c=1$) were the probabilities for a kind of internal forward and backward motion creating the overall forward motion with speed v in the x direction. K. Knuth [18] has also discussed this type of model. In this note, we wish to examine in more details built-in assumptions associated with this 2x2 matrix models and its possible implications on spin. In particular, we consider different orientations of bouncing photons and try to find a relationship between zitterbewegung in the rest frame of a box moving with speed v in the x direction and the lab frame. Different orientations of the bouncing photons seem to lead to different zitterbewegung patterns with the Dirac type being represented by Doppler shifted photons bouncing along the x axis.

2x2 Matrix Model

Given the quadratic energy momentum equation (1), one can divide by E and use $p/E=\cos(a)$ and $m/E=\sin(a)$. Then $\cos(a)=\cos^2(a/2)-\sin^2(a/2)$ and $\sin(a)=2\sin(a/2)\cos(a/2)$ and the linear equation can be written as a 2x2 matrix equation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p & m \\ m & -p \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix} = E \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here the p - m matrix is taken as the Hamiltonian and a velocity matrix as $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

as a velocity matrix. Using $V(t)=\exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt)$ one can find that the operator V varies periodically in time with various terms (i.e. zitterbewegung). K. Huang [10] argued that this periodic motion could physically describe spin.

Let us examine (2) in more detail. First, let us consider the energy in terms of the two components of the eigenvector.

$$.5 \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p & m \\ m & -p \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix} = .5m\sqrt{1+v}/\sqrt{1-v} + .5m\sqrt{1-v}/\sqrt{1+v}$$

The two terms, corresponding to the terms in the 2-eigenvector are exactly the Doppler shifted energies of a photon bouncing back and forth in the x direction in a box moving with velocity v in the x direction. Here m/2 is taken to be the frequency of the photon in the rest frame of the box. Thus,

$$.5m\sqrt{1+v}/\sqrt{1-v} + .5m\sqrt{1-v}/\sqrt{1+v} = m/\sqrt{1-v^2} \text{ i.e. the energy of a particle and}$$

$$.5m\sqrt{1+v}/\sqrt{1-v} - .5m\sqrt{1-v}/\sqrt{1+v} = mv/\sqrt{1-v^2} \text{ i.e. the momentum of particle}$$

Thus, the Dirac style 2x2 linear matrix equation of a particle appears to be equivalent to a photon bouncing back and forth in the x direction. This raises the question: What about having a photon bounce back and forth in a box in a direction other than the x direction? The box would still move with speed v in the x direction. For example, in the rest frame of the box, the photon would make an angle of b with the x axis.

Bouncing up ("u" for up) $p'_y = p_y$

$$\begin{pmatrix} p'_x \\ p'_y \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -v \\ -v & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p_x \\ p_y \end{pmatrix} \text{ where } B = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2} \text{ and } p^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2.$$

A similar expression holds for p' where p' is the photon energy in the rest frame of the box (which is also its momentum when c=1).

Bouncing down -p'_y = -p_y "d" denotes the photon bouncing down.

$$\begin{pmatrix} -p'_x \\ p'_y \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -v \\ -v & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p_x \\ p_d \end{pmatrix}$$

This leads to:

$$0 = p_x u + p_x d - v(p_u + p_d) \text{ or } P_{total} = v(E_{total}) \text{ where } P_{total} \text{ is the total momentum.}$$

Let $p' = m/2$, then

$$m/B = -v(P_{total}) + E \text{ or } E_{total} = m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$$

$$\text{Also } P_{total} = mv/\sqrt{1-v^2} \text{ and } (1) E^2 = P_{total}^2 + m^2$$

Thus, a photon bouncing back and forth in any direction in a box which in turn moves with speed v in the x direction will give rise to relativistic energy and momentum equations of a particle with a rest mass $m = 2p'$ where p' is the photon energy in the box rest frame. The feature to keep in mind, however, is that the relativistic particle equation that one obtains is for a particle

moving in the x direction i.e. there is no momentum in the y direction. In the physical picture of the bouncing photon there is p_y both up and down. It cancels overall, but that is not the same as having no p_y . This becomes important when one converts (1) into a linear matrix equation. It has already been shown that this equation only corresponds to a photon bouncing back and forth in the x direction and so excludes all other orientations of bouncing. Thus, the Dirac type linear 2x2 matrix equation (2) excludes what seem to be many physical types of “bouncing photons”. A priori, if the Dirac type 2x2 linear matrix equation corresponds to a photon bouncing back and forth in the x direction, there is no reason to exclude scenarios including photons bouncing back and forth in other directions. The Dirac type 2x2 linear matrix equation has been shown to have zitterbewegung. Thus, it seems that the other orientations of bouncing should also have zitterbewegung and perhaps corresponds to different spins than the Dirac spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

Calculating Zitterbewegung of Different Bouncing Photon Orientations

It would be good to try to calculate the zitterbewegung of photons bouncing with different orientations in a box moving with speed v in the x direction. If one considers the Hamiltonian of (2) with $p=0$ together with the velocity matrix $\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix}$

one can see that the velocity eigenvectors are (1,0) and (0,1) corresponding to eigenvalues of 1 and -1. These eigenvalues may describe bouncing motion in any direction. There is no specific direction specified. Thus, one can calculate $V(t) = \exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt)$ using $H(p=0)$ to obtain a $V(t)$ zitterbewegung equation in the rest frame of the box. This will give zitterbewegung along the axis of orientation in the rest frame of the box. One should then be able to transform to the lab frame for a box moving with speed v in the x direction.

$$V(t') = \left\{ \cos^2(mt') - 2\sin^2(mt') \right\} V + i \sin(mt') \cos(mt') \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

The imaginary portion may signify motion perpendicular to the motion along the “axis which makes an angle of b with the x axis”. It has to be treated with care, however, because it has a vanishing expectation value even when the real part does not.

One could take the expectation value with (1,0) the “up” moving direction to find $\langle V(t') \rangle$ and then use $ds'/dt' = \langle V(t') \rangle$ to find $s'(t')$ where s is along a line which makes an angle b with the x axis. The expectation of the imaginary part with (1,0) is 0 so it contributes perhaps in a different way. $x'(t') = \cos(b) s'(t')$ and $y'(t') = \sin(b) s'(t')$

One can see that different values of b give different values of $y'(t')$ which does not change under the Lorentz transformation for a box moving in the x direction. Thus, it seems that different angles of b may be giving different zitterbewegung patterns.

One can use Lorentz transformations to then find a trajectory in the lab. The expectation using (0,1) is the negative of this. It is not clear if dx'/dt' is really what is wanted because of cancellations between dx'/dt' for (1,0) and (0,1)

It was shown in [2] that one could even find an X matrix in the rest frame of the box such that $[H(p=0), X] = V$.

$$X = aI + d H(p=0) + \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1/m & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{where } a \text{ and } d \text{ are arbitrary constants.}$$

$$\text{Let } M = H(p=0)$$

Now $[M, X] = V$ and $X(t) = \exp(iMt) X \exp(-iMt)$ or:

$$X(t) = \cos^2(mt) X - (1/m) i \sin(mt)\cos(mt)V + (1/m^2)\sin^2(mt) \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 1/m \\ 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

One can take expectation values of $X(t)$ with (1,1) where this vector makes an angle of b with the x axis in the rest frame of the box. Taking an expectation with (1,0) gives 0 so this $X(t)$ is a combination of the up and down motions.

$$\langle X(t) \rangle = \cos^2(mt) (1/m) + (1/m) (1/m^2)\sin^2(mt)$$

Then $\langle X(t) \rangle \cos(b) = x'$ and $\langle X(t) \rangle \sin(b) = y'$. (It is possible that the imaginary part might ultimately contribute to x' and y' , but this has to be studied in more detail.)

Here one can see that for different values of b , the y' is different. The expectation of the imaginary part with (1,1) vanishes. It, however, does not vanish with (1,0) or (0,1) and so might actually contribute in some way, but this would have to be studied in more detail.

It should be noted that the $dx'/dt' = \langle V(t') \rangle$ and $X(t')$ do not appear to be the same and do not necessarily even describe the same thing. Both can give trajectories $x'(t')$ which may be related to physical zitterbewegung of the particle. It should be noted that there is no X matrix for $p > 0$ (i.e. outside the box rest frame) such that $[H(p > 0), X] = V$.

In the lab frame: $y'(t') = y(t)$ and

$$\begin{vmatrix} |x| \\ |t| \end{vmatrix} = B \begin{vmatrix} |1-v| & |x'| \\ |v+1| & |t'| \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{where } B = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2}$$

Or $x = B(x' + vt')$ and $t = B(vx' + t')$. Using a computer, one could then obtain a numerical graph of $x(t)$ in the lab for different orientations parametrized by the angle b . This should describe the zitterbewegung in the lab frame. Given that zitterbewegung is supposed to be related to spin,

this might describe particles with different spins even though one is not using the Dirac type 2x2 linear matrix equation (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the 2x2 linear matrix energy eigenvalue equation, which is similar to the Dirac equation, appears to be consistent only with a photon bouncing back and forth along the x axis where the speed v is also along this axis. This raises the question of photons bouncing back and forth along an arbitrary axis making an angle b with the x axis in the rest frame of a box moving with speed v in the x direction. These arbitrary bouncing photons give a total energy and total momentum which are equivalent to a relativistic particle moving in the x direction. One should, however, not use the 2x2 matrix Dirac type equation to describe these because they have momentum components perpendicular to the x axis (which cancel for total momentum), but should contribute to overall energy. In the 2x2 Dirac type equation, the total energy comes from a photon bouncing in the x direction, there is no y direction energy. The arbitrary bouncing photons, however, may have some relevance. One can go into the rest frame of the box and calculate $V(t)$ and $X(t)$ and find zitterbewegung effects here. These can then be Lorentz transformed to the lab frame. It is possible that these arbitrary bouncing directions could represent different spins, if in fact zitterbewegung is supposed to be related to spin.

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